

Original article

PUBLIC DEBT SUSTAINABILITY IN POST-2000 EU MEMBER STATES WITH EURO ADOPTION: A PENALIZED SPLINE REGRESSION APPROACH

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Abstract: *The sustainability of public debt has gained renewed attention in the aftermath of the 2008 financial crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, and recent geopolitical tensions. This paper investigates long-term debt sustainability in Eurozone countries that acceded post-2000 analyzing fiscal dynamics from 2000–2023. Using penalized spline regression in a semi-parametric time series framework, we evaluate fiscal dynamics while incorporating institutional determinants such as political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism and macroeconomic indicators like the unemployment rate (as a percentage of the total labor force). Our results show that Croatia, Latvia, Malta, and Slovenia have exhibited relatively sustainable debt policies, while other countries show weaker or statistically insignificant sustainability signals. Among the models tested, the one including political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism performed best, suggesting that institutional stability is a key determinant of fiscal sustainability. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating institutional dimensions into debt analysis and provide valuable insights for policymakers seeking to enhance fiscal resilience in the Eurozone's newer member states.*

Keywords: Public Debt, Debt Sustainability, Penalized Spline Regression, Economies of European Countries That Joined the Eurozone after 2000

JEL classification: H63, H68, C52, E62

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1. Introduction

As global economies experience mounting financial pressures, comprehending the sustainability of public debt has turned into an essential topic. Excessive public debt can threaten economic stability and hinder growth, potentially leading to financial crises, defaults, or inflation. Effectively managing public debt allows governments to maintain necessary public services, safeguard social welfare programs, and avoid creating excessive financial obligations for succeeding generations. Debt levels that are sustainable provide the fiscal flexibility essential for managing economic crises, like the one caused by the recent global pandemic, which has put immense strain on national budgets and public finances.

The pandemic has highlighted the urgent need for sound fiscal management, with governments ramping up taking on debt to fund public health initiatives and economic revitalization. However, excessive debt accumulation must be carefully managed to prevent long-term economic instability. Beyond domestic concerns, sustainable debt is essential for maintaining public trust and securing credibility in international financial markets, allowing nations to access necessary funding when needed. By prioritizing debt sustainability, policymakers can better prepare for future economic disruptions and ensure long-term fiscal resilience, supporting both national and global economic equilibrium.

Within the framework of European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, examining the sustainability of public debt has become increasingly significant as these nations navigate fiscal challenges, economic shocks, and long-term stability. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted public debt levels in many of these countries, as governments increased borrowing to finance public health measures, support economic recovery,

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and protect vulnerable populations. Balancing the need for immediate fiscal intervention with long-term sustainability is crucial for maintaining investor confidence, ensuring economic stability, and supporting continued development. For these nations, managing public debt at sustainable levels is essential to avoid excessive borrowing costs and secure the resources needed for infrastructure investments and public services.

The geopolitical landscape has also added complexity to public debt management for Eurozone countries that joined after 2000, particularly with the ongoing challenges posed by conflicts such as the war in Ukraine. The war has exacerbated economic uncertainties, impacting energy prices, trade dynamics, and overall economic stability. For these countries, increasing defense and humanitarian expenditures further strains already stretched public finances, making the need for sound debt management strategies even more pressing. Sustainable debt levels will help these countries navigate the economic disruptions caused by such crises, ensuring they maintain fiscal resilience while avoiding long-term instability. It is essential for these countries to manage increased spending and debt effectively to ensure long-term prosperity and stability.

This paper aims to evaluate the sustainability of public debt in European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000. The empirical analysis will focus on various critical factors, including the primary surplus, the ratio of net public debt, public debt expenditures, fluctuations in economic cycles (real GDP changes), unemployment rate (as a percentage of the total labor force) and political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism. Data for these variables from 2000 to 2023 will be sourced from trusted organizations like the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank. To assess the sustainability of debt, the study will use spline regression, offering a detailed examination of how fiscal policies interact with economic cycles and highlighting the distinct features of each country within the dataset.

This paper is arranged into five sections, each designed to offer a comprehensive view of public debt sustainability in European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000. The first section offers a brief introduction to the topic. The second section presents a review of the existing literature, exploring the key theories, concepts, and empirical findings that form the basis of research on public debt sustainability. The third section outlines the research methodology, providing a clear and detailed explanation of the data sources and analytical framework used in the study. It describes the statistical techniques employed, such as spline regression, to evaluate the sustainability of public debt, and explains the rationale behind the selection of these methods and the data collection process. This section also discusses the choice of relevant variables and their importance in analyzing fiscal policies within the European context. The fourth section presents a comprehensive empirical analysis, concentrating on the sustainability of public debt of European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000. It examines the results of the analysis, considering factors such as economic cycles, primary surpluses, and political stability, and how these elements interact to influence public debt levels and sustainability. A comparative overview of the countries in the sample is also provided, offering valuable insights into their unique fiscal dynamics. The final section summarizes the key findings and presents the main conclusions of the study. It discusses the implications of the results for fiscal policy design, public debt management, and suggests directions for future research. By synthesizing the analysis, this section highlights the challenges and opportunities faced by Eurozone countries in maintaining sustainable public debt levels, offering practical recommendations for policymakers aiming to strengthen fiscal resilience and economic stability.

2. Literature review

Debt sustainability is built upon the principle of the idea that a country can only maintain a certain level of debt if its economy can grow at a pace that allows it to meet its debt obligations. A government is considered to be in debt sustainability if its primary surplus (revenues minus non-interest expenditures) is enough to meet the interest payments on its debt, while the economy grows at a pace that outpaces the real interest rate. If the primary surplus is inadequate, the government may face a situation where its debt grows faster than the economy, leading to unsustainable levels of debt (Blanchard, 1990).

In recent decades, the empirical literature has used a variety of methods to assess debt sustainability. One of the most common approaches is the "stationarity" approach, which tests whether a country's fiscal balance (the primary surplus) is sufficient to stabilize the debt ratio. If the primary surplus is stationary and the debt-to-GDP ratio is stable or decreasing over time, then the country's debt can be considered sustainable (Trehan and Walsh, 1991). However, this approach has been criticized for its reliance on a linear relationship between debt and fiscal surpluses, which might not hold in real-world economies, particularly in times of economic distress or when debt levels become extremely high.

A novel approach for testing the sustainability of public debt was introduced, arguing that traditional methods often prematurely declare a policy unsustainable. Instead, it was proposed to examine how the primary surplus responds to changes in the debt-to-GDP ratio. If the primary surplus as a percentage of GDP increases in a linear or

greater manner with rising debt, public debt can be considered sustainable (Bohn, 1998). The logic behind this test is straightforward: if a government boosts its primary surplus in response to a rising debt-to-GDP ratio, it is taking corrective measures to ensure its solvency. This concept was formally validated by Bohn under the assumption of a constant response coefficient (Bohn, 1998). Later, this framework was extended by incorporating a time-varying response coefficient, offering a more flexible model (Canzoneri et al., 2001). A comprehensive and insightful overview of this topic can be found in Beqiraj et al. (2018). In recent years, several studies have delved into the concept of nonlinear fiscal behavior, specifically exploring the phenomenon of “fiscal fatigue,” which refers to a reversal in the behavior of the primary balance when debt ratios reach very high levels. At this point, instead of continuing to improve, the response weakens and eventually turns negative (Ghosh et al., 2013; Checherita-Westphal and Zdarek, 2017; Fournier and Fall, 2017).

The dynamics of public debt sustainability in the context of European economies, focusing on the challenges posed by both external and internal economic factors, have been explored by Stoian et al. (2022). The study emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach to fiscal policy, considering the fluctuating nature of public debt and the role of governmental interventions in mitigating fiscal stress. By analyzing various economic indicators, including primary surplus, debt-to-GDP ratio, and political stability, a comprehensive model for assessing debt sustainability is proposed. It is argued that maintaining fiscal flexibility is vital for managing public debt, especially during worldwide economic disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The need for ongoing policy adjustments and institutional reforms to ensure long-term debt sustainability is also stressed, offering insights particularly relevant for European countries navigating complex economic conditions (Stoian et al., 2022).

Recent, an advanced penalized spline regression method was employed to examine public debt sustainability across 25 EU economies from 2000 to 2019, exploring the complexities and variations in debt sustainability analysis. The study notes that the link between public debt and fiscal policy changes depending on the debt-to-GDP ratio. Specifically, the response of the primary surplus to rising public debt varies significantly depending on economic conditions and debt thresholds, suggesting that governments can only implement corrective fiscal policies when debt exceeds certain limits. The study emphasizes the complexity of debt sustainability and the relevance of applying flexible econometric models to capture these non-linear relationships, providing a more detailed and nuanced perspective on public debt management in a dynamic economic context (Owusu et al., 2023).

The approach used in this research relies on the methods introduced by Bohn (1998), Berti et al. (2016) and Owusu et al. (2023). Based on data collected annually spanning from 2000 to 2023, we develop models to analyze European countries that became part of the Eurozone after 2000. All models are semi-parametric, capturing the non-linear link between the primary balance and the debt-to-GDP ratio, a relationship emphasized by previous research (Greiner and Kauermann, 2007). To estimate these models, we apply penalized spline regression, a method that provides more accurate and stable estimates compared to traditional ordinary least squares (OLS), as proven by previous research (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1990; Ruppert et al., 2003). This approach ensures that the complexities in the data are better captured, leading to more reliable results. This approach allows for greater flexibility in capturing complex patterns in the data.

3. Data and methodology

This study explores how European countries that adopted the Euro after 2000 have managed the accumulation of public debt. We examine data from 2000 to 2023, sourced from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank. Our methodology is derived from the frameworks established by Greiner and Fincke (2016). In particular, we investigate how the primary surplus expressed as a proportion of GDP, reacts to changes in the public debt ratio, which is also expressed as a percentage of GDP. To ensure a comprehensive understanding of country-specific heterogeneities, we incorporate control variables for institutional determinants such as political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism and macroeconomic indicators like the unemployment rate (as a percentage of the total labor force).

The unemployment rate (as a percentage of the total labor force) is a measure that represents the proportion of people within the labor force who are actively seeking employment but are unable to find work. This is an important indicator, but it can sometimes be misleading. Ironically, low unemployment rates may mask significant poverty within a nation, while high rates of unemployment rates can occur even in countries with strong economic progress and reduced levels of poverty. In countries lacking unemployment benefits or welfare systems, people often rely on precarious and unstable jobs to make a living. In contrast, in nations with well-established social safety nets, workers have the luxury of waiting for more suitable or desirable job opportunities. However, prolonged high unemployment generally signals inefficiencies in how a country allocates its resources. Youth unemployment is a particularly urgent issue in many economies. Young people today face growing uncertainty about their ability to

transition smoothly into the labor market, and this uncertainty can lead to disillusionment, which has negative consequences not only for individuals but also for communities, economies, and society at large. Unemployed and underemployed youth often face challenges in making meaningful contributions to their countries' development and have fewer opportunities to fully participate as citizens. As a result, they tend to spend less, invest less, and are typically unable to advocate effectively for improvements in their circumstances or communities. Furthermore, high levels of youth unemployment and underemployment limit innovation and hinder the ability of countries and companies to gain competitive advantages by investing in human capital, which ultimately affects future economic growth. Consequently, the unemployment rate is a vital indicator for evaluating a country's progress in achieving the sustainable development goal of promoting long-term, inclusive growth, as well as ensuring full and productive employment and decent work for all.

The indicator of political stability and the lack of violence/terrorism evaluates how the public perceives the likelihood of political instability or violence driven by political factors, including terrorism, within a given country. This metric is represented as a percentile rank, enabling a comparison of a country's stability and security with that of other nations across the globe. A rank of 0 represents the lowest possible degree of stability and safety, indicating significant risk of instability, while a rank of 100 denotes the highest level of stability and security, signaling a country with minimal political unrest. To ensure that the rankings remain consistent over time, the percentile scores are adjusted periodically to account for shifts in the countries included in the World Governance Indicators (WGI). This adjustment process guarantees that the rankings reflect a stable and similar metric, even as the global context of nations under evaluation evolves and changes.

3.1. Why Include Political Stability and Unemployment?

While it may initially seem counterintuitive to include variables such as political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, or unemployment rate in debt sustainability models for Eurozone countries – a region considered relatively stable compared to other parts of the world – recent methodological frameworks from the European Commission explicitly emphasize the need for comprehensive, multidimensional risk assessments (European Commission, 2024). The updated debt sustainability analysis framework for the Eurozone mandates that, in addition to deterministic and stochastic debt simulations, supplementary indicators must be integrated to capture liquidity risks, solvency risks, and institutional factors, including governance and political risks (Bouabdallah et al., 2023). Thus, modern debt sustainability analysis frameworks for the Eurozone no longer rely solely on traditional fiscal variables but recommend assessing risks across at least three dimensions: macroeconomic factors, institutional determinants, and market dynamics (CEPR, 2023).

The inclusion of institutional variables, such as political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, is justified by the fact that debt sustainability depends not only on the “ability to pay” (reflected in fiscal and macroeconomic indicators) but also on the “willingness to pay” – that is, the capacity and political resolve of governments to implement sustainable fiscal policies in volatile political and social contexts (European Commission, 2024). Even in countries with low incidence of violence or terrorism, episodes of political instability, social unrest, or regional tensions can rapidly erode investor confidence, raise borrowing costs, and generate short- to medium-term refinancing risks, as demonstrated by Greece's experience during the sovereign debt crisis (European Commission, 2015). Furthermore, the European Commission explicitly recommends complementing fiscal risk assessments with governance and structural indicators to prevent systemic risk underestimation (Bouabdallah et al., 2023).

Regarding macroeconomic indicators like unemployment rates, recent literature and EU institutional reports highlight that persistently high unemployment can exacerbate fiscal pressures by reducing tax revenues and increasing social expenditures, thereby amplifying debt sustainability risks (IMF, 2023). Labor market shocks can also propagate to economic growth and governments' ability to maintain primary surpluses, which are critical for long-term debt trajectories (European Central Bank, 2021). For instance, in countries such as Slovenia or Slovakia, where industrial sectors dominate, rising unemployment can trigger fiscal imbalances that are not immediately visible in traditional debt-to-GDP metrics (Eurostat, 2023).

By integrating these additional variables, the analysis aligns with the ECB's and European Commission's updated methodological standards while ensuring a robust assessment capable of capturing emerging risks not reflected in purely fiscal or macroeconomic models (Bouabdallah et al., 2023). This multifactorial approach adds significant value, enabling policymakers to anticipate and manage potential vulnerabilities – including those stemming from institutional or market factors – and adopt more resilient fiscal policies (European Commission, 2024).

The relevance of these additional variables becomes even clearer when examining the specific countries included in this analysis: Croatia, Cyprus, Estonia, Greece, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Slovakia and Slovenia. Despite their shared membership in the Eurozone, these countries display considerable heterogeneity in terms of economic structure, institutional quality, and exposure to external shocks. For example, Greece has experienced acute episodes of political instability and social unrest, which have directly impacted its debt servicing costs and market access, especially during the sovereign debt crisis (European Commission, 2015). Cyprus, while generally stable, faces unique geopolitical risks related to the division of the island and its proximity to regional tensions, which can influence investor sentiment and fiscal planning (European Commission, 2024). The Baltic states – Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania – are exposed to specific security concerns due to their geographic location and historical context, making the inclusion of governance and security indicators particularly relevant for assessing their fiscal resilience (European Commission, 2024).

Malta and Slovenia, though enjoying relative political stability and low unemployment rates in recent years, are small, open economies highly sensitive to external shocks, such as fluctuations in tourism or financial sector volatility (European Central Bank, 2012). Slovakia and Croatia have both undergone significant structural reforms since joining the Eurozone, but remain vulnerable to shifts in political dynamics and labor market conditions, which can quickly alter fiscal projections (Eurostat, 2023).

Therefore, incorporating institutional and macroeconomic variables into debt sustainability models for these countries is not only consistent with the latest EU fiscal surveillance frameworks, but also essential for capturing the full spectrum of risks that may affect their public debt trajectories. This approach ensures that country-specific vulnerabilities – whether stemming from governance, political stability, labor market shocks, or external threats – are adequately reflected in sustainability assessments, leading to more informed and effective policy recommendations (European Commission, 2024).

3.2. Penalized Spline Regression Methodology

Penalized spline regression is a flexible statistical technique designed to model non-linear relationships between variables, overcoming the limitations of traditional linear regression (Eilers & Marx, 1996). Unlike linear models, which assume constant relationships across all values of independent variables, penalized spline regression allows the relationship to vary smoothly, adapting to complex patterns in the data (Wood, 2017). This method is particularly valuable for analyzing economic phenomena, such as the dynamic interplay between fiscal balances and public debt, where non-linearities and time-dependent effects are common (Hastie & Tibshirani, 1990).

The general model is defined as: $y_i = f(x_i) + \varepsilon_i$, where y_i represents the dependent variable, x_i denotes the independent variable, $f(x_i)$ is a smooth spline function and ε_i is the error term. The function $f(x)$ is estimated by minimizing the penalized residual sum of squares: $minimize \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - f(x_i))^2 + \lambda \int [f''(x)]^2 dx \right\}$. Here, λ is a smoothing parameter that controls the trade-off between model fit and smoothness. The penalty term $\lambda \int [f''(x)]^2 dx$ penalizes abrupt changes in the spline's curvature, ensuring a smooth fit (Eilers & Marx, 1996).

Penalized spline regression employs rigorous validation criteria to ensure model accuracy and robustness. One of the most widely used methods is Generalized Cross-Validation (GCV), which optimizes the smoothing parameter (λ) by minimizing out-of-sample prediction error, balancing model complexity and predictive performance (Wood, 2017; Eilers & Marx, 1996). For moderate-sized models, Akaike Information Criterion and Bayesian Information Criterion are preferred, as they penalize the effective degrees of freedom to prevent overfitting (Ruppert et al., 2003).

3.3. The econometric models

The econometric models applied in this paper are derived from the methods used by Bohn (1998), Berti et al. (2016), and Owusu et al. (2023). For the time series analysis, we adopted a semi-parametric model, which is outlined below:

$$PB_t = \beta_0 + f(Debt_{t-1}) + \beta_1 Expend_t + \beta_2 GDP_t + \beta_3 Unemployment_t + \varepsilon_t \text{ (for model 1), respectively}$$

$$PB_t = \beta_0 + f(Debt_{t-1}) + \beta_1 Expend_t + \beta_2 GDP_t + \beta_3 Political_S_t + \varepsilon_t \text{ (for model 2).}$$

In both models, PB_t represents the primary surplus (as % of GDP), whereas $Debt_{t-1}$ represents the debt ratio from the previous period, reflecting the common practice of setting budget plans a year ahead. The variables $Expend_t$ and GDP_t denote public expenditure and real GDP variations, respectively, with the latter serving as an indicator of the business cycle. The long-term trend was removed from the data series smoothed using the Hodrick-Prescott filter to compute these values.

The variable $Unemployment_t$ is a control variable that reflects the specific economic characteristics of the countries analyzed and represents the unemployment rate as a percentage of the total labor force, which can influence economic performance and fiscal policy. The variable $Political_S_t$ (political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism) is a control variable that reflects the overall political environment of the country, capturing the impact of political stability on economic performance, investor confidence, and fiscal policy effectiveness. This variable is essential for understanding how political factors influence public debt sustainability and economic growth. $f(Debt_{t-1})$ is a smoothing function that, although unknown, is continuous and derived from the data, and is applied to the previous period's debt ratio. The coefficients β_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$ are associated with the variables $Expend_t$, GDP_t , and Z_t , respectively. The term ε denotes the error term.

The connection between the primary surplus ratio and public debt is typically linear for most variables, with the exception of the lagged debt variable, $Debt_{t-1}$. The primary surplus ratio is influenced by the lagged debt variable in a non-linear manner (Greiner and Kauermann, 2007). This means that the relationship between the public debt and the primary surplus is not constant or linear over time, and the impact of changes in public debt on the primary surplus varies depending on the level and past values of the debt. To capture this dynamic relationship, a time-varying coefficient is used. This coefficient measures the responsiveness of the primary surplus to changes in the public debt ratio, and it varies over time, indicating the sensitivity of the primary surplus to changes in the debt ratio. Greiner and Fincke argue that nonlinear relationships like this can be approximated by linear models with time-varying coefficients, especially when changes in the underlying parameters occur gradually (Greiner and Fincke, 2016). This approach allows for a simpler model while still capturing the essence of the nonlinear dynamics. Granger also supports this concept, suggesting that gradual changes in parameters allow for the use of time-varying coefficients to approximate more complex nonlinear models (Granger, 2008). For public debt to be considered sustainable, the reaction of the primary surplus to changes in the debt ratio must be positive, indicating that an increase in debt leads to an improvement in the primary surplus. Moreover, the magnitude of this response should be sufficiently large on average to ensure that the government is able to generate enough surplus to manage and eventually reduce the debt over time. A positive and sufficiently large reaction coefficient signals that the fiscal policy is responsive enough to maintain public debt at sustainable levels, preventing it from becoming unsustainable in the future.

The analysis employs penalized spline regression because it offers a more effective approach for modeling non-linear relationships in comparison to traditional ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. While OLS is widely used for estimating linear relationships, it struggles to capture the complexity of non-linear patterns, which are often present in economic data such as the relationship between public debt and fiscal policy. Penalized spline regression overcomes this limitation by applying smooth, flexible functions that can adapt to the non-linear nature of the data while avoiding overfitting (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1990; Wood, 2000; Ruppert et al., 2003). The method works by introducing a penalty term that controls the smoothness of the spline, striking a balance between fitting the data well and maintaining model simplicity. This flexibility results in more robust and accurate estimates, particularly when dealing with complex, real-world data where relationships are rarely perfectly linear. To improve the reliability of our results, we examine different combinations of variables to ensure that the relationships captured by the model are not driven by a specific selection of predictors. By examining different model specifications, we account for potential variations in how different factors influence the outcomes, improving the robustness of the findings.

The analysis is based on data provided by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank.

4. Empirical findings

This paper offers an empirical examination of public debt sustainability in European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000. Before discussing the results, we begin by providing a brief overview of the variables we analyze and their relevance to the study. Then, we proceed with the time series estimations, which are used to evaluate the sustainability of public debt in these nations.

4.1. Data summary

The empirical study uses annual data from European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, covering the period from 2000 to 2023. To handle missing values, we applied a basic AR(1)-based imputation technique. Specifically, we estimated the first-order autoregressive coefficient using available data, and extrapolated missing values accordingly: forward (using the previous value and the AR(1) coefficient) or backward (by dividing the next value by the same coefficient). This pragmatic approach allowed us to preserve the dynamic structure of the series while minimizing bias due to imputation. The trends and patterns of the key variables are visually presented in Figures 1 to 6, providing a clear representation of their dynamics over the study period.

The primary surplus

The primary surplus is calculated by subtracting government spending (excluding interest payments) from government income, and it is presented as a percentage of GDP. This data, which covers European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, spans the period from 2000 to 2023 and is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: The evolution of primary surplus (% of GDP) for European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, covering the period from 2000 to 2023

The graphs in the image depict the dynamics of the primary surplus (% of GDP) for European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, highlighting significant fluctuations influenced by economic and political factors. Countries like Greece and Malta experienced substantial deficits, especially during economic crises, followed by fiscal adjustments that led to recovery. On the other hand, economies such as Estonia and Lithuania maintained a relatively stable path, though still affected by global recessions. Cyprus and Latvia exhibited sharp oscillations, suggesting greater vulnerability to economic shocks, while Slovakia and Slovenia showed a more balanced fiscal trajectory, albeit with periods of fiscal deterioration. Overall, the data reveals a complex process of fiscal adjustment, with consolidation during growth periods and higher deficits during crises, reflecting the interaction between fiscal policies and economic cycles.

Additionally, it is worth mentioning that all the countries analyzed reported deficits during the COVID-19 health crisis. This period saw a sharp rise in government expenditures due to the pandemic, paired with a decline in revenues as a result of economic disruptions, leading to a widespread deterioration in fiscal balances.

Unemployment, total (% of total labor force)

Figure 2 shows the unemployment rate as a percentage of the total labor force for European countries that became part of the Eurozone after 2000, spanning from 2000 to 2023.

Figure 2. Unemployment, total (% of total labor force) for European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, covering the period from 2000 to 2023

The graphs illustrate the evolution of unemployment in several European countries between 2000 and 2023. A significant increase in unemployment is observed during the 2008-2009 financial crisis, with notable spikes in countries such as Greece, Latvia, and Cyprus. These countries experienced dramatic rises in unemployment, followed by longer recovery periods. In contrast, countries like Malta and Slovenia had more moderate fluctuations, without extreme increases.

In the years that followed, most countries managed to reduce unemployment rates, although the pace of recovery varied. Greece and Cyprus had slower recoveries, while the Baltic states, like Latvia and Lithuania, rebounded more quickly to lower levels. Slovakia and Estonia displayed moderate fluctuations, indicating periods of economic instability. Overall, the 2008 crisis had a significant impact on the European labor market, but some economies proved more resilient than others.

Political stability and absence of violence/terrorism

Figure 3 presents the trends in political stability and absence of violence/terrorism for European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, spanning from 2000 to 2023.

Figure 3. Political stability and absence of violence/terrorism for European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, covering the period from 2000 to 2023

The graphs indicate the level of political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism on a scale from 0 to 100, with higher values signaling greater stability. Malta shows the highest values, ranging between 95 and 100, although a gradual decline is noticeable after 2010. Slovenia and Slovakia initially had high values, between 80 and 90, but Slovakia experienced a sharp decline after 2015, dropping below 70. Greece has the lowest values, ranging from 30 to 50, indicating chronic political instability, particularly after the 2008 economic crisis. Cyprus and Latvia show unstable values, fluctuating between 50 and 80, suggesting alternating periods of stability and turmoil. The Baltic countries, Estonia and Lithuania, experienced moderate fluctuations, maintaining values between 70 and 85, indicating a relatively stable level of political stability. Overall, while some countries maintained high levels of stability, others saw significant declines, reflecting the impact of economic and political crises.

4.2 Estimating spline regression

The outcomes of estimating the econometric models for the European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000 in our sample, using unemployment, total (% of total labor force) and political stability (as well as absence of violence/terrorism) as control variables, are provided in detail in Tables 1 and 2. The models displayed in these tables were chosen based on two key criteria: the lowest generalized cross-validation (GCV) statistic and the highest adjusted R-squared (Adj. R²) value. The results shown reflect those cases where the smooth function's coefficient is found to be statistically significant. Notably, for Estonia, the model that includes the unemployment rate (as a percentage of the total labor force) does not yield statistically significant results.

Estimated regression coefficients

The estimated equations, along with their corresponding results, are presented in detail in Tables 1 and 2 below.

Unemployment, total (% of total labor force)

Table 1: Coefficients for models that include unemployment, total (% of total labor force) as a control variable (dependent variable: primary surplus as % of GDP)

Variables	HR	CY	GR	LV	LT	MT	SK	SI
Constant	-5.749 *** (1.476)	-0.893 (3.604)	-15.140 ** (5.960)	-3.941 *** (1.355)	-0.052 *** (0.013)	-2.898 (2.731)	-4.137 (3.232)	-6.710 *** (1.519)
PB_{t-1}	0.218 *** (0.073)	-0.050 (0.136)	0.049 (0.112)	0.083 (0.085)	-0.063 (0.056)	0.256 ** (0.092)	-0.040 (0.121)	0.008 (0.050)
$Debt_{t-1}$	0.046 ** (0.021)	-0.089 (0.077)	0.001 (0.023)	0.054 *** (0.011)	-0.026 * (0.012)	0.085 ** (0.032)	0.048 (0.058)	0.092 ** (0.031)
$Expend_t$	-0.860 *** (0.110)	-1.166 *** (0.188)	-0.958 *** (0.147)	-0.707 *** (0.100)	-0.948 *** (0.061)	-1.172 *** (0.139)	-0.664 *** (0.104)	-0.975 *** (0.057)
GDP_t	0.164 (0.151)	-0.862 (0.944)	-0.00005 (0.072)	0.278 (0.172)	-0.258 *** (0.088)	-1.591 * (0.896)	0.178 (0.165)	-0.019 (0.165)
$Unemployment_t$	-0.162 (0.134)	-0.752 * (0.389)	0.267 (0.209)	0.008 (0.130)	-0.187 *** (0.045)	-0.754 (0.571)	0.077 (0.231)	0.042 (0.253)
sm_t	F.stat. 7.403 ***	F.stat. 9.326 ***	F.stat. 3.83 **	F.stat. 5.448 **	F.stat. 11.24 **	F.stat. 8.622 ***	F.stat. 7.883 ***	F.stat. 5.327 ***

Standard error in brackets

***p<0.01; **p<0.05; *p<0.1.

The data presented in Table 1 indicate that the coefficients for Unemployment, total (% of total labor force) are statistically significant in only two countries: Cyprus and Lithuania. In both instances, the significantly negative coefficients suggest that, during periods of rising unemployment, the primary surplus ratio tends to decrease, or the fiscal deficit increases. This implies that higher unemployment can lead to a deterioration in the fiscal balance, as it typically results in reduced tax revenues and increased public spending on social benefits. For the remaining countries, the coefficients are not statistically significant, preventing any conclusions about whether Unemployment, total (% of total labor force) has a positive or negative effect on public debt sustainability.

The coefficients for net debt are found to be statistically significant in the case of five countries (Croatia, Latvia, Lithuania Malta, and Slovenia), indicating a meaningful relationship between net debt and the primary surplus in these nations. In four of these countries (Croatia, Latvia, Malta, and Slovenia), the coefficients are positive, indicating that as the debt-to-GDP ratio increases, the primary surplus ratio also rises. These findings suggest that public debt is sustainable in these countries during the period analyzed. In contrast, for one country (Lithuania), the coefficient is significant and negative, implying that the country follows an unsustainable debt policy. Additionally, by analyzing the deviation $f(.)$ from the average coefficient for $Debt_{t-1}$ (Figure 4), which illustrates the progression of the smooth term, we can observe that Lithuania's response of the primary surplus ratio to changes in the debt ratio has consistently risen throughout the entire period, even though the values remain negative. In the case of Croatia, the plot of the smooth terms shows that the values are concentrated around the average reaction coefficient, indicating a weak sustainability policy. For Latvia, and Slovenia, despite an overall declining trend, the values stayed positive throughout the entire period. In Malta's case, the smooth term shows an upward trend for a period, followed by a subsequent decline. In Malta's case, the smooth term shows an upward trend for a period, followed by a subsequent decline. The downward trend indicates that the government gave less priority to stabilizing public debt.

Figure 4. The variation $f(\cdot)$ from the mean coefficient for $Debt_{t-1}$ in the European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, based on models estimated using the variable unemployment, total (% of total labor force)

By examining the coefficients for government expenditure, we find significantly negative values across all countries, which implies that, during periods of increased public spending, the primary surplus ratio tends to shrink. This suggests a clear inverse relationship between government expenditure and fiscal balance, indicating that higher public expenditure is associated with a reduced capacity to generate primary surpluses, potentially leading to larger fiscal deficits in the long run.

The coefficients for the lagged primary surplus are found to be statistically significant at the 5% significance level in the case of two countries (Croatia and Malta), indicating a notable relationship between the previous period's primary surplus and the current primary surplus in these countries.

Political stability and absence of violence/terrorism

Table 2 : Coefficients for models that include political stability as a control variable (dependent variable: primary surplus as % of GDP)

Variables	HR	CY	EE	GR	LV	LT	MT	SK	SI
Constant	-0.005	-7.262	-7.923	-5.359	-2.863	1.437	-3.756	-0.368	-7.894
	***		**	**	**				***

	(0.0005)	(5.437)	(3.492)	(6.036)	(1.346)	(2.217)	(6.046)	(3.384)	(2.293)
PB_{t-1}	0.297	-0.016	-0.266	-0.061	0.073	0.039	0.260	-0.052	0.005
	***		**				**		
	(0.054)	(0.156)	(0.123)	(0.123)	(0.074)	(0.060)	(0.104)	(0.107)	(0.048)
$Debt_{t-1}$	0.029	-0.048	-0.103	-0.010	0.052	-0.024	0.063	0.067	0.076
	**				***		*		**
	(0.011)	(0.088)	(0.083)	(0.023)	(0.010)	(0.014)	(0.030)	(0.058)	(0.032)
$Expend_t$	-0.872	-1.049	-0.726	-1.004	-0.730	-0.976	-1.204	-0.656	-0.965
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
	(0.088)	(0.208)	(0.093)	(0.136)	(0.079)	(0.063)	(0.153)	(0.099)	(0.054)
GDP_t	0.223	0.087	-0.462	-0.074	0.239	0.004	-1.228	0.181	-0.061
	*		*		*				
	(0.114)	(0.872)	(0.219)	(0.056)	(0.127)	(0.117)	(0.937)	(0.135)	(0.143)
$Political_S_t$	-0.085	0.055	0.084	0.104	-0.014	-0.045	-0.020	-0.039	0.017

	(0.014)	(0.066)	(0.048)	(0.063)	(0.018)	(0.030)	(0.065)	(0.036)	(0.026)
sm_t	F.stat.	F.stat.	F.stat.	F.stat.	F.stat.	F.stat.	F.stat.	F.stat.	F.stat.
	51.3	6.162	3.435	2.883 *	15.44	8.032	5.69 ***	6.584	9.329
	***	***	*		***	***		***	***

Standard error in brackets
***p<0.01; **p<0.05; *p<0.1.

The data presented in Table 2 indicate that the coefficients associated with political stability are statistically significant for only one country (Croatia), suggesting that the influence of political stability on the primary surplus is evident in this particular case, while it does not show a significant effect in the other countries analyzed. In this case, the significantly negative coefficients suggest that the primary surplus ratio decreases, or the deficit increases, during periods of greater political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism. This implies that enhanced political stability might be associated with a smaller fiscal surplus or a larger fiscal deficit.

When analyzing the coefficients for net debt, the results are similar to those obtained from Model 1 (the model with the control variable for unemployment, total (% of total labor force)), revealing comparable trends and patterns in the data. This consistency suggests a stable relationship across the models. Specifically, for Croatia, Latvia, Malta, and Slovenia, the coefficients are positive and statistically significant, indicating that these countries maintain a sustainable public debt. In the case of Latvia, although there is an overall declining trend in the data, the coefficients remained positive throughout the entire period, reflecting a relatively weak, yet persistent, commitment to debt sustainability. In Malta, while the overall trend shows an increase in the primary surplus, the response remained negative for several years following the period analyzed in our study. Nonetheless, the upward trajectory in the time path suggests that the Maltese government has been increasingly focused on addressing and stabilizing public debt, potentially signaling a shift toward more effective fiscal policies in the long term.

Figure 5. The variation f(.) from the mean coefficient for $Debt_{t-1}$ in the European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, based on models estimated using the variable political stability and absence of violence/terrorism

The estimation results for government expenditure and business cycle variables reveal consistent patterns across all countries analyzed. Specifically, the significantly negative coefficients for government expenditure align with theoretical expectations, suggesting that higher public spending is associated with a reduction in the primary surplus. This outcome indicates that, despite fluctuations in government expenditure, public debt remains sustainable, as the negative relationship suggests that governments are effectively managing their fiscal policies to maintain stability and avoid excessive debt accumulation.

To provide a concise overview of the empirical results, Table 3 summarizes the assessment of public debt sustainability for each of the European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, covering the period from 2000 to 2023. The classification is based on the statistical significance and sign of the net debt coefficient in both Model 1 and Model 2. Results are largely consistent across the two models: Croatia, Latvia, Malta and Slovenia exhibit signs of public debt sustainability in both specifications, while Lithuania is the only country for which debt appears unsustainable—this result is observed only in Model 1. For the remaining countries, no definitive conclusion can be drawn due to statistically insignificant coefficients or non-significant model performance.

Table 3 : Summary of Public Debt Sustainability Assessment by Country for Models 1 and 2

	HR	CY	EE	GR	LV	LT	MT	SK	SI
Model 1	YES	I	NA	I	YES	NO	YES	I	YES
Model 2	YES	I	I	I	YES	I	YES	I	YES

Legenda: YES = the country shows a statistically significant and positive relationship between debt and primary surplus (public debt is considered sustainable); NO = the country shows a statistically significant and negative relationship (public debt is considered unsustainable); I = Inconclusive (the coefficient of net debt is not statistically significant and no conclusion can be drawn about sustainability); NA = the model is not statistically significant.

4.3 Validation of the estimated models

The validation of the model is conducted using two key criteria: adjusted R-squared and cross-validation. Adjusted R-squared assesses the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the model, while accounting for the number of predictors included. This adjustment ensures that the measure not only reflects the model's fit but also its complexity, penalizing the inclusion of unnecessary predictors. Cross-validation, on the other hand, evaluates the model's generalizability by partitioning the data into subsets. The model is trained on one subset and tested on the remaining subsets, which helps to assess how well the model performs on unseen data, ensuring its robustness and reliability. Additionally, cross-validation involves excluding one data point at a time to evaluate the model's prediction accuracy, further enhancing its robustness and preventing overfitting.

The optimal outcomes occur at the point where the cross-validation criterion achieves its minimum value and the adjusted R-squared is maximized. A lower cross-validation value indicates better model fit and prediction accuracy, while a higher adjusted R-squared reflects greater explanatory power. The ideal model balances both, ensuring robust predictions and powerful explanatory capacity.

The results of the model validation criteria for the European countries that became part of the Eurozone after 2000, based on the two models analyzed over the period from 2000 to 2023, are comprehensively summarized in Tables 4 and 5. These tables provide a detailed comparison of the performance and reliability of the models, incorporating the key validation metrics. The validation criteria, which include adjusted R-squared and cross-validation measures, are used to evaluate the fit, complexity, and generalizability of the models, offering insights into their predictive accuracy and robustness across the countries under study. The findings presented in these tables

reflect the extent to which the models successfully capture the dynamics of public debt sustainability in the Eurozone countries analyzed.

Table 4 : The results for Adj. R² and GCV tests for models incorporating unemployment, total (% of total labor force) as a control variable (dependent variable: primary surplus as % of GDP)

	HR	CY	GR	LV	LT	MT	SK	SI
Adj. R ²	0.948	0.937	0.925	0.925	0.957	0.951	0.941	0.982
GCV	0.699	1.364	2.167	0.421	0.489	0.840	1.054	0.351

Table 5 : The results for Adj. R² and GCV tests for models incorporating political stability as a control variable (dependent variable: primary surplus as % of GDP)

	HR	CY	EE	GR	LV	LT	MT	SK	SI
Adj. R ²	0.958	0.916	0.832	0.935	0.928	0.951	0.943	0.946	0.982
GCV	0.514	1.845	0.916	2.046	0.407	0.591	0.986	0.978	0.358

By thoroughly analyzing the empirical results derived from the econometric models estimated for European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, and utilizing statistical variables that capture the unique economic and political characteristics of these countries (such as unemployment rate, political stability, and the absence of violence/terrorism), we find that the model incorporating political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism demonstrates superior performance. Specifically, this model yields the lowest generalized cross-validation (GCV) values and the highest adjusted R-squared (Adj. R²) values, making it the most accurate representation of the underlying data-generating process for the majority of countries in our sample. These findings suggest that the model accounting for political stability and security is more reliable for assessing public debt sustainability than the alternative model based solely on unemployment rates. Consequently, it can be considered a more effective and informative tool for guiding policy decisions related to fiscal management and debt sustainability in the Eurozone countries.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we examine the sustainability of public debt in the countries of the European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000, focusing on the period from 2000 to 2023. This timeframe has been characterized by substantial economic, political, and social transformations as these countries navigated their path toward integration into the European Union and the adoption of the Euro. The challenges these nations faced included implementing economic reforms, addressing structural vulnerabilities, and adapting to the demands of EU membership. The 2008 global financial crisis, the economic fallout from the COVID-19 pandemic, and more recently, geopolitical conflicts like the war in Ukraine, have all intensified the challenges faced in fiscal policy decision-making. These events have placed considerable strain on public finances and debt management strategies in these countries. This analysis aims to explore how the public debt dynamics of these nations have transformed in response to these challenges and assess the long-term implications for their economic stability and fiscal policy frameworks.

In evaluating the sustainability of public debt in the European countries that became part of the Eurozone after 2000, we utilized the methodology proposed by Greiner and Fincke (2016), as it is well-suited to the distinct economic and institutional features of these countries. This technique supports an in-depth evaluation of the long-term sustainability of public debt, considering both historical and structural contexts. Additionally, our econometric model is improved through the addition of control variables that represent key institutional and macroeconomic factors. These variables include political stability and the absence of violence or terrorism, unemployment (as a percentage of the total labor force), all of which are essential for understanding the broader economic environment in these countries.

By including variables such as unemployment (as a percentage of the total labor force), political stability, and the absence of violence or terrorism, our goal is to encompass the wider institutional framework that impacts fiscal policy and the sustainability of public debt. Unemployment provides insight into the health of the labor market and its effect on public finances, while political stability assesses the reliability and consistency of the political environment, which plays a vital role in shaping economic strategies. The absence of violence or terrorism is also crucial, as it affects both the economic landscape and governance structures. This comprehensive framework ensures that our analysis of public debt sustainability accounts for the complex interaction between economic strategies and institutional elements.

Our evaluation of the four models indicates that model 2, which incorporates political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism as control variables, offers the most precise depiction of the underlying data generation process. This conclusion is strongly supported by its exceptional performance, as evidenced by the lowest generalized cross-validation (GCV) values, which reflect the model's ability to generalize well to unseen data, and the highest adjusted R-squared, suggesting that it explains the variability in the data more effectively than the other models. These results demonstrate that the inclusion of these institutional factors significantly enhances the model's explanatory power and robustness.

The significantly negative coefficient for political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism in Model 2 for Croatia points to the fact that, as political stability improves and the threat of violence or terrorism diminishes, there may be a reduction in the need for higher fiscal surpluses or a less stringent fiscal policy. This could indicate that a more stable and secure political environment allows for greater fiscal flexibility and reduces the pressure on the government to maintain a high primary surplus in response to public debt. It implies that political stability and security may foster a more conducive environment for managing public finances, potentially leading to more sustainable debt levels over time.

With respect to public debt sustainability, the empirical findings show that only a limited number of countries, namely: Croatia, Latvia, Malta, and Slovenia have implemented public debt policies that can be considered sustainable to some extent during the period under analysis, across both models studied. These countries have adopted fiscal strategies that enable them to manage their debt more efficiently, despite the economic challenges posed by the global financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic. In contrast, for Lithuania, within Model 1, the coefficient is both significant and negative, suggesting that the country is engaged in a debt policy that is not sustainable. This result implies that Lithuania may need to adopt more flexible fiscal policies and implement institutional reforms to support long-term fiscal sustainability. For the remaining countries in the sample, the lack of statistical significance suggests that the assumption of an unsustainable public debt policy cannot be dismissed.

In comparison with previous studies (Greiner and Fincke, 2016; Stoian et al., 2022; Owusu et al., 2023) this research offers a more nuanced understanding of public debt sustainability by applying a penalized spline regression model to better capture the non-linear relationship between fiscal balances and debt. By integrating time-varying coefficients, institutional determinants such as political stability and the absence of violence, as well as macroeconomic indicators like the unemployment rate, this study provides a more comprehensive and dynamic framework for assessing public debt sustainability in European countries.

These findings carry important policy implications. The evidence that political stability and the absence of violence significantly influence fiscal sustainability suggests that governments must not only focus on macroeconomic indicators but also strengthen institutional resilience. When a country is politically stable and free from violence, it is more likely to manage its debt well. But in parts of Europe, growing political tensions and social unrest make this harder. Future debt sustainability strategies should therefore integrate not just fiscal discipline, but also take action to reduce social problems, improve political cooperation, and build trust in public institutions. In the long run, managing debt responsibly means combining smart financial policies with efforts to keep society united and stable.

Although our research is subject to certain limitations, particularly the small data sample, the findings are in line with the existing body of literature and provide important insights into the fiscal policies of European countries that joined the Eurozone after 2000. While annual data enables a broader historical perspective, it may overlook short-term fiscal dynamics or immediate policy responses to economic shocks. Future research could address this limitation by integrating quarterly data and incorporating additional diagnostic tests to refine the robustness of the results. Nevertheless, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of how these countries manage public debt and fiscal stability, offering a foundation for further analysis and policy discussions.

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